

Streamlined isolation of *E. coli* biofactory metabolites using centrifugal extraction and partition chromatographic techniques. New hydroxytyrosol derivatives

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ABSTRACT

Microbial production of bioactive molecules provides a promising alternative to traditional isolation or chemical synthesis approaches, enabling high-yield production of pure compounds without the need for heavy-metal catalysts, harsh conditions, or complex plant-based processes. Hydroxytyrosol (HT), a potent antioxidant with significant pharmacological properties, has attracted considerable interest due to its broad applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and food industries. While *Escherichia coli* systems have been effective for HT production, optimization of extraction yield and recovery process remain a challenge. Furthermore, isolation of HT and its metabolites continues to suffer from inefficiencies even when biosynthetic pathways are successful. Centrifugal techniques such as annular centrifugal extraction and partition chromatography methods e.g., Annular Centrifugal Extraction - ACE, Countercurrent chromatography - CCC, Centrifugal Partition Chromatography - CPC offer advantages over traditional methods, including the absence of solid stationary phases, reduced organic solvent use, speed, and scalability. However, these techniques have been underutilized in biotechnology workflows. Additionally, existing procedures often employ simplistic analytical methods, which lead to loss of valuable data for pathway monitoring, validation and metabolite discovery. This study presents a comprehensive workflow for the production, extraction, isolation, and identification of HT and derivatives from metabolically engineered *E. coli* biofactories. The workflow combines ACE for media extraction with CPC for high yield and purity HT isolation. It also emphasizes the analysis and structural elucidation of HT metabolites by means of HRMS/MS and 1 & 2D NMR, facilitating biosynthetic pathway monitoring and discovery of novel HT metabolites with potential enhanced biological activity. Using this approach, 23 compounds were isolated and identified contributing to the completion of the complex biosynthetic route of HT synthesis from L-tyrosine. This is first reported of direct isolation of pure HT metabolites from *E. coli* biofactories and to our knowledge the first application of liquid-liquid centrifugal techniques in the treatment of biotechnological materials.

1. Introduction

Hydroxytyrosol (3,4-dihydroxyphenylethanol, HT) is a prominent natural phenolic compound and even though it can be found in a variety of fruits and vegetables, HT is a characteristic compound of olive fruits (*Olea europaea*) and olive oil [1,2]. HT has garnered significant attention due to its significant biological and pharmacological properties while it is considered one of the most potent natural antioxidants [1,3–5]. It is

recognized for its wide range of biological effects, including cardioprotective, anti-cancer, neuroprotective, antimicrobial, and endocrine beneficial effects [6–9]. In brief, the key properties that make HT particularly attractive include its potent antioxidant activity, effectively scavenging free radicals [3–5]; its ability to reduce the risk of coronary heart disease and atherosclerosis [1,6–8]; its role in preventing LDL oxidation, platelet aggregation, and inhibiting 5- and 12-lipoxygenases [6,10,11]; its contribution to bone formation and maintenance [12];

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and its ability to control both human and plant bacterial and fungal pathogens [6,11,13,14]. As a key component of the health-promoting Mediterranean diet, HT has gained recognition for its disease-preventing potential, further supported by a recent health claim by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) regarding its protective effect against plasma low-density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation [11].

Despite being a native constituent of olive fruits and olive oil, HT is mainly derived from the hydrolysis of more complex compounds, such as oleuropein and ligstroside, which occur during olive ripening, olive oil production or over time after storage of olive products. Several factors influence the final HT concentration including olive variety, regional microclimate, soil quality, and the extraction method. The final concentration in olive oil typically ranges from 0.2 to 29.0 mg/kg [5]. While HT is already used in dietary supplements and cosmetic products, its value as a component of nutraceuticals or in functional foods and as a therapeutic drug is growing [12,13]. Although it is less commercially recognized compared to other popular antioxidants such as ascorbic acid or coenzyme Q10, HT boasts higher antioxidant activity and is rapidly absorbed into the bloodstream [14]. Regardless of its potential, the large-scale commercial availability of this valuable antioxidant is limited due to the lack of effective production methods [2].

Three major approaches for HT production have been developed i.e. extraction from natural sources, chemical synthesis, and biotechnological synthesis [15]. Natural sources, such as olive oil industry by-products (including olive oil mill wastewater, solid by-products of olive oil production, and olive leaves), provide abundant starting materials for HT extraction. Nonetheless, despite the plethora of these by-products, the extraction process faces several challenges. These include high costs due to low yields and the impure nature of the HT obtained, which is further complicated by seasonal and climatic variations [15,16]. An alternative strategy involves the chemical synthesis of HT using structural analogues (such as tyrosol, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, eugenol, homovanillyl alcohol, 3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine, etc.) as starting materials [2,16–23]. However, these chemical methods present issues such as expensive substrates, toxic catalysts, harsh reaction conditions, complex steps, and low yields, making them unsuitable for industrial-scale production [16,24]. Biotechnological synthesis, through metabolic engineering and synthetic biology, presents a promising alternative. By using genetically engineered microorganisms to produce bioactive compounds, this approach has the potential to overcome the limitations of traditional methods, either by reconstructing natural biosynthetic pathways or by designing entirely new ones [2].

To achieve HT biosynthesis through biotechnological means, several pathways have been designed, which are extended from l-tyrosine or its precursor 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate (4-HPP) [2,16,25–27]. To commercially optimize the biosynthesis of HT and other phenolic compounds, a favorable way is to reconstruct the entire biochemical pathway in a genetically tractable microorganism [16]. Therefore, the construction of microbial cell factories has become a promising alternative approach to produce HT [16,28]. Biological synthesis using microorganisms (*E. coli*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Yarrowia lipolytica*, etc.) has advantages over in vitro enzymatic and chemical syntheses, since it does not require expensive cofactors, it confers regioselectivity and stereoselectivity, while being an environmentally friendly method [25].

E. coli has been widely used to synthesize diverse natural bioactive compounds. Primarily, various attempts have been made to produce HT in *E. coli* biofactories either directly from glucose or after supplementation with various precursor molecules. In all these cases various approaches were utilized, though with different efficiencies. In a straightforward process, Choo, et al. (2018) [29], produced HT through l-tyrosine (hereafter tyrosine) by the overexpression of the codon optimized version of a tyrosine decarboxylase, a tyrosine oxidase and a 4-hydroxyphenylacetate 3-hydroxylase (*HpaBC*). In a different approach, Li, et al. (2018) [2], produced HT from 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate, exploiting the activities of a ketoacid decarboxylase, an alcohol dehydrogenase and a *HpaBC*. An alternative production process was

followed by Li, et al. (2019) [24], who set-up a whole cell catalysis exploiting enzymatic activities of aromatic amino acid aminotransferase, l-glutamate dehydrogenase, α -keto acid decarboxylase and aldehyde reductase. The HT pathway was further engineered by Yao, et al. (2020) [30], to include a version of *HpaBC* engineered through directed evolution to increase its activity. In a previous study of our research group [28], Trantas, et al. exploited a dual pathway to produce HT from tyrosine, taking advantage of the dual substrate specificity of tyrosinase (TYR) and aromatic acetaldehyde synthase (AAS), and an endogenous acetaldehyde reductase (ALR). Specifically, we have tailored the so-called HT pathway with tyrosine as a precursor, expressing the respective genes to construct metabolically engineered regular strains such as BL21(DE3) and HMS174(DE3), leading to highest titers of HT and achieving equimolar concentration of HT to tyrosine as precursor, reaching the level of 1.76 mM (270.8 mg/L) as analyzed by LC–HRMS. Additionally, expressing genes not only to produce HT, but also for the endogenous tyrosine overproduction, it became possible to create a metabolic effect permitting the redirection of primary metabolic flux from externally added glucose to a tyrosine pool that proved to be saturating the first enzymatic step of the engineered pathway from tyrosine to HT. Moreover, the addition of a selected ALR, overexpressed along with the other abovementioned genes, led to an additional increase in HT production efficiency. A single-step bioconversion using precursor compounds with structural similarity to HT has been reported with high volumetric productivity and product titer; however, the expensive substrate is a major bottleneck to industrial scale production by this approach [15]. HT, tyrosol, salidroside, resveratrol, rosmarinic acid and other phenolic compounds, have been previously synthesized in metabolically engineered microbes, mainly by *E. coli* [16].

Nonetheless, the downstream processing of HT produced in *E. coli* biofactories presents also significant challenges during extraction, separation, and purification. The primary difficulties lies in the complexity of the fermentation broth which contains a mixture of cells, proteins, metabolites, salts, and other impurities [31], complicating the isolation of HT. Therefore, its extraction necessitates suitable solvent that selectively extracts HT without co-extracting impurities. Liquid-liquid extraction can lead to emulsion formation, hindering phase separation and reducing efficiency. Another critical aspect is that HT is typically present in low concentrations compared to other components, requiring highly efficient separation techniques to achieve good recovery yields [32]. In the case of biofactories like *E. coli* structurally similar byproducts or intermediates may also be produced, co-eluting with HT during chromatography and further complicating purification. In addition, HT's highly polar nature makes it more difficult to separate from other similarly polar compounds in the broth. This polarity also limits the choice of solvents, as HT tends to partition into aqueous phases rather than organic solvents. Therefore, the accumulation of undesired metabolites can reduce the overall yield of HT and affect cell viability. Moreover, HT is sensitive to oxidation, light, and heat, which can lead to degradation during processing [32] especially in prolonged procedures. It is important to highlight that many laboratory-scale extraction and purification techniques are expensive or difficult to scale up for high or even industrial production. Developing cost-effective and scalable methods is essential for commercial viability [33]. Lastly, solvent toxicity raises safety and environmental concerns, driving the need for greener extraction methods. Therefore, optimizing the extraction and purification of HT from *E. coli* biofactories requires addressing these interrelated challenges by selecting efficient separation methods, considering scalability, and investigating environmentally friendly alternatives.

Among these lines, centrifugal chromatographic techniques based on the liquid-liquid separation principle for both extraction and isolation could be a competent alternative. Specifically, Annular Centrifugal Extraction (ACE) is a continuous flow, high-throughput liquid-liquid extraction technique based on the Taylor-Couette flow phenomenon [34] which is mainly utilized in the area of nuclear waste,

pharmaceuticals, wastewater treatment and hydrometallurgy [35]. This special type of fluid motion occurs because the liquids flow between the two coaxial cylinders of the instrument and the inner cylinder spinning while the outer remains stationary. The rotation of the inner cylinder disrupts the smooth flow of the liquids by creating vortices that enhance mixing and subsequently facilitate the dispersion of the one liquid into the other [36]. The intense mixing and centrifugal separation ensure high mass transfer rates, leading to effective extraction of compounds of interest [36]. The use of ACE and generally annular centrifugal contactors offers significant advantages in terms of efficiency, purity, scalability, and therefore sustainability. Their ability to handle continuous processing, gentle separation, and precise control makes them a valuable tool for research and industrial applications in complex mixtures and high volumes [37,38]. The reduced volume of solvent required for extraction and continuous processing increases throughput [37,39], making the process more cost-effective which is crucial for large-scale production. Despite its potential, ACE remains underutilized in biotechnology workflows although it offers significant advantages for the treatment of fermentation broths for the recovery of specific compounds.

On the other hand, Centrifugal Partition Chromatography (CPC) is a liquid-liquid chromatographic technique based on the partitioning between two immiscible liquid phases that stay at equilibrium. CPC or FCPC belongs to the family of countercurrent chromatography or CCC techniques and it comprises a technological variant related to the retention mechanism of stationary phase. More in detail, two immiscible liquids that stay at equilibrium, forming a biphasic liquid system, are put into the contact, emulsified, and separated multiple times, to form the phenomenon of theoretical plates [40,41]. One of the phases is put into the rotor and retained as a stationary phase, while the other phase is pumped through as a mobile phase. Due to the shear forces that are present between both phases, the mobile phase is dispersed within the stationary phase, thus providing an interfacial area for mass transfer. The mobile phase penetrates the stationary phase, and hence the separation of the solutes, contained in a mobile phase, is achieved according to their partition coefficients (K_D), expressed as the ratio of their concentrations in the stationary phase to their concentration in the mobile phase [40,41]. The retention mechanism of stationary phase is based on hydrostatic force, formed by the centrifugal field in the rotor in one-axis centrifuge [40–42]. CPC excels in handling compounds with a broad spectrum of polarities, ensuring comprehensive separation without any degradation or loss of biomass [40,41,43]. Notably, CPC boasts a remarkable injection capacity, allowing for the processing of multi-gram quantities of sample, making it an invaluable tool for large-scale preparative applications in isolation and purification [41,44]. Its ability to maintain the integrity of sensitive compounds while achieving high-resolution separation and high injection capacity at the multi-gram scale, underscores its significance in modern chromatographic practices [41,43].

Building on the above, we present here a systematic multistep protocol for the biotechnological production, extraction, concentration, purification, and *de novo* structural elucidation of HT and metabolites. These compounds are produced by metabolically engineered *E. coli* biofactories utilizing a modified l-tyrosine/L-DOPA pathway. For the first time, this protocol incorporates two liquid-liquid, centrifugal, continuous-flow chromatographic techniques i.e. ACE and CPC in biotechnology culture media treatment. Due to their efficiency and scalability, the isolation and unambiguous identification using spectrometric (HRMS/MS), and spectroscopic (1 and 2 D NMR) techniques, of HT and its intermediate metabolites, and/or end-products was possible. This can significantly aid in pathway optimization by enabling efficient monitoring of the process and optimizing metabolic flux. This methodology aims to generate new insights into the mechanistic understanding of microbial metabolic biotransformations during fermentation but also to introduce centrifugal chromatography methodologies in biotechnological workflows.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials and reagents

Ethylacetate (EtOAc; Macron Fine Chemicals™ Leicestershire, England), methanol (MeOH; Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK), and cyclohexane (c-Hex; Sigma-Aldrich, United-Kingdom) that were used in CPC separation were of analytical grade. Milli-Q-plus ultra-pure water system from Millipore (Milford, MA) was used throughout the study to prepare all aqueous solutions. MeOH and ACN of HPLC gradient grade (Carlo-Erba) as well as formic acid (FA, Fischer chemicals) were used for HPLC-DAD analysis. Vanillin standard (98 % purity) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (United-Kingdom). Preparative and analytical TLC was performed on Silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ 20 cm × 20 cm plates purchased from Merck Millipore (Massachusetts, USA). The standard compounds (purity >98 %) used for the HPLC qualitative and quantitative analysis were purchased from Chembiotin (Greece) (Hydroxytyrosol, Tyrosol standards). For UPLC—Orbitrap-MS analysis ACN, H₂O and acetic acid that were used were LC-MS grade (Fisher Chemical). Deuterated methanol (MeOD) for NMR analysis was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (United-Kingdom).

2.2. Metabolic engineering methods and reagents

2.2.1. Construction of *E. coli* metabolically engineered strain

A metabolically engineered strain of *E. coli* capable of producing HT was constructed and named BL21-pACYC-PcAAS (abbreviated as B11T) [28]. Briefly, using the primer combination GTT ACC ATG GGC TCC ATC GAT AAT CTT ACT G / GGA TCC CTC AAA CCA GAG CAG AGA CAT GG, a 1680-bp DNA fragment encoding for an Aromatic Acetaldehyde Synthase (AAS) from *Petroselinum crispum* was cloned from root cDNA. Subsequently, it was inserted into the pACYC expression vector (Novagen, Merck-Millipore), utilizing the *Nco*I and *Bam*HI restriction enzymes to give the pACYC-PcAAS expression plasmid.

2.2.2. Biotechnological HT production

The metabolically engineered *E. coli* strain B11T was employed to bio-transform of DOPA into HT. From 114.4 gr of DOPA (4.8 mM) 67.52 gr of HT (3.64 mM) was produced giving a yield of 76 %. In more detail, the B11T *E. coli* strain was grown in a fed-batch mode at a 50 L semi-industrial scale bioreactor (LP351, Bioengineering AG), where vessel temperature, agitation, pH and aeration were tightly controlled. The M9 growth medium was prepared in the 50 L bioreactor's vessel and sterilized on site. The reaction was initiated with the inoculation of the medium with a 2 L overnight culture of B11T strain grown in Lysogeny Broth. B11T was let to grow until optical density reached OD₆₀₀=1 and the inducer (Isopropyl β-d-1-thiogalactopyranoside, IPTG) was added to a final concentration of 200 μM. The culture was let to grow for additional 3 h and DOPA was added to a final concentration of 4 mM. The system was left to continuous steering for additional 12 h expecting a 1:1 bio-transformation efficiency. By the end of the reaction the B11T cells were separated from the HT-enriched growth medium, by a high-speed tubular centrifuge (CEPA), and was frozen until purification. Detailed description is presented in the Supporting Information (1.1).

2.3. Isolation and analytics

2.3.1. Annular centrifugal extraction (ACE)

The large-scale extraction of biophenols from the fermentation broth was performed using the pilot scale Annular Centrifugal Contactor (model BXP190) system (mono-stage unit) (Rousselet-Robatel Kromaton, Annonay, France). The apparatus consists of a casing and a bowl driven by a motor directly coupled to the extractor pendular shaft. The bowl has an internal diameter of 190 mm with a useful volume of 4.2 L. The two liquid phases are mixed in the annular space of the extractor and are separated in the weir system, which consists of a stable light

phase weir of 90 mm and an interchangeable heavy phase weir of 100 mm. The motor is fed by a variable frequency drive to achieve variable speed operation with the maximum acceptable speed of 2900 rpm. Both heavy and light phases were pumped through the extractor with two ATEX FLUX eccentric worm-drive pumps with FBM 4000 Ex Motor and flow rate up to 75 L/min (FLUX-GERATE GmbH, Maulbronn, Germany) connected to the two solvent inlets of the apparatus. During the recovery process of phenolics from culture media using the ACE technique, ethyl acetate (EtOAc) was chosen as the optimal extraction solvent.

2.3.2. Centrifugal partition chromatography (CPC) separation

The fractionation of the phenolic fraction was carried out on a Fast Centrifugal Partition Chromatograph FCPC1000® (Rousselet-Robatel Kromaton, Anonay, France) equipped with a preparative column. The FCPC1000 rotor is made of 45 circular partition disks engraved with 32 partition cells (555 mL per cell) and the total column volume capacity is 1000 mL. The partition cells are interconnected by capillary ducts, the latter representing a volume of 156 mL (dead volume). Rotation speed could be adjusted from 200 to 1200 rpm, thus producing a stable centrifugal force field in the partition cells up to 161 g at 1000 rpm. The mobile phase was pumped through the stationary phase either in the descending or in the ascending mode through a via a LabAlliance Preparative pump. For the fractionation of the phenolics fraction, sample was introduced into the column through a PEEK preparative scale sample injector 3725 (Rheodyne, Rohnert Park, CA, USA) equipped with a 50 mL sample loop, while fractions were collected using a Büchi B-684 fraction collector (Büchi Labortechnik AG, Flawil, Switzerland). The system was coupled to an UV detector SPECTRA SYSTEM UV 2000, Thermo Scientific (Illkirch, France). All experiments were conducted at room temperature (20 ± 2 °C). The LC system was controlled by Clarity™ 5.4 (DataApex, Prague, Czech Republic).

10 sets of biphasic systems consisting of n-heptane or c-hexane, EtOAc, MeOH, EtOH or isoProp and H₂O were selected for performing partition coefficient evaluation (analytical description in Supporting Information, Table 2) and the test samples were analyzed by HPLC-DAD. Based on the HPLC chromatograms and the partition coefficient values (K_D) calculated, the CPC experiment was carried out in elution extrusion mode by using the biphasic system c-Hex/EtOAc/MeOH/H₂O in proportion 1:9:2:8 (v/v/v/v). Initially, the column was filled with the stationary phase (the upper phase) on descending mode at a flow rate of 15 ml/min and set the rotation speed at 250 rpm. Then, the rotation speed was maximized at 900 rpm, and the mobile phase was pumped through the column with a flow rate of 10 ml/min on descending mode. After the system equilibration, the retention volume of the stationary phase was calculated at 720 ml giving a high S_f value of 72.0 %. Then, 5.145 g of the crude extract was diluted in 50 ml mixture of the two phases (ratio 1/1 upper phase/lower phase) and injected via a 50-ml injection loop. The volume of mobile phase used for the elution step was 2.000 ml while the experiment was completed by passing 1.200 ml of the stationary phase in descending mode (extrusion step). The rotation speed and flow rate were kept stable at 750 rpm and 15 ml/min, respectively, during the whole experiment. The total analysis time lasted approximately 180 min, and finally, 143 fractions of 20 ml were collected. The merging of the fractions resulting from the CPC was based on the TLC profile of each fraction, finally giving 11 combined fractions. More information about the fractions derived is given in Supporting Information (Table 3).

2.3.3. HPLC-DAD/ELSD analysis

All fractions derived from CPC isolation were subjected to profiling using different techniques in parallel. Useful information about the richness and the complexity of the fractions was retrieved. To cover as much as possible the chemical variety of compounds, an LC system hyphenated to DAD and ELSD detectors in series was employed. Chromatographic analysis was performed on an Agilent HPLC 1260 Infinity II system (Santa Clara, United States), equipped with a 1260 Infinity II Quaternary pump, an autosampler with thermostat, a column

compartment, and a 1260 Infinity II Diode Array Detector (DAD), as well, a 1260 Infinity II Evaporative Light Scattering Detector (ELSD). Metabolites were monitored at 210, 235, 254, 280 and 366 nm, and UV spectra were recorded between 190 and 600 nm. Separations were performed on a Supelco Discovery HS RP C18 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 µm particle size) from Sigma-Aldrich equipped with a matching pre-column. The injection volume was 20 µL and during analysis samples were stored at 40 °C. Data processing was performed with the Agilent OpenLab CDS software. Detailed description is presented in the Supporting Information (1.3).

2.3.4. UPLC-ESI-MS/MS (Orbitrap) analysis

In parallel the 11 CPC fractions were subjected to UPLC–HRMS and HRMS/MS analysis to detect minor components due to high LC-MS sensitivity. Also, the use of a high resolution and high accuracy MS analyser provided useful structural information of the compounds. Moreover, the pure compounds after isolation were also analysed in MS and MS/MS level for identification purposes aided NMR interpretation. The analysis was performed on an Acquity® UPLC system (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled with an LTQ-Orbitrap XL hybrid mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The mass spectrometer was equipped with electrospray ionization (ESI) source and operated in negative and positive mode. The analysis was performed with an LC gradient consisting of H₂O with 0.1 % formic acid (FA) (solvent A) and ACN (solvent B).

The mass spectra data were acquired in the full scan m/z range of 115–1000, in negative and positive mode at a resolving power of 30,000 and data-dependent MS/MS events were acquired, using an electrospray ionization source (ESI). In both modes, the data-dependent acquisition was simultaneously performed using a collision induced dissociation C-trap (CID) with normalized collision energy at 35 V and a mass resolution of 10,000. For identification and dereplication the following ranking criteria were employed: R_t , EC, $10 \leq RDBeq \leq 20$, mass range m/z 100 - 1000 Da, mass tolerance ≤ 5 ppm; HRMS/MS spectra of the selected peaks and identification of the fragmentation pattern and literature. Detailed description is presented in the Supporting Information (1.4).

2.3.5. Preparative hplc-uv and TLC based isolation

After profiling, the purification of compounds from CPC fractions were performed on a preparative HPLC chain consisted of two Lab Alliance preparative 36 Pumps (State College, USA), a UV Flash 06S DAD 800 Detector of ECOM (Prague, Czech Republic) and injection valve Rheodyne 7755–027 equipped with 1 mL loop (Target Analysis, Thessaloniki, Greece). The separation was run on a Supelco supelcosil™ LC-18, 25 cm × 21.2 mm, 5 µm (Pennsylvania, USA) preparative HPLC column while the fractions were collected manually based on UV chromatograms. The HPLC system was controlled by Clarity™ 5.4 (DataApex, Prague, Czech Republic). Each sample was dissolved either in MeOH or ACN to achieve a concentration of 150 mg/mL before being injected using a 1 mL volume capacity loop. Samples of 50–150 mg/mL were introduced through a 1 mL injection loop, and distinct elution methods were employed for each metabolite during chromatographic separations.

In certain fractions, i.e. fr2, fr3, and fr11 the secondary purification was carried out with prep-TLC chromatography. From the TLC experiments the sub-fractions fr2a, fr3a, fr3b, fr11a, fr11b afforded pure compounds. The coding of the isolated compounds refers to the two chromatographic purification steps. More specifically, the number refers to the first purification step indicating the corresponding CPC fraction (e.g. fr9) while the letter refers to the elution order in the secondary purification step performed either by prep-HPLC or prep-TLC (e.g. fr.9a>fr.9b>fr.9c>fr.9d). The analytical and preparative Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was performed on Merck 60 F₂₅₄ pre-coated normal phase silica gel plates (Merck Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) and developed with DCM/MeOH 90:10 (v/v). Regarding prep-TLC

purification of the fractions from CPC, 20 mg of each fraction were dissolved in DCM or ACN and the TLC plate was developed in a glass chamber. The revelation was firstly achieved by using UV light at 254 and 365 nm, and then TLC spots were visualized after being sprayed by a vanillin (5 % w/v in ethanol) – H₂SO₄ (50 % v/v in methanol) solution and heated at 100–120 °C for 2–3 min.

2.3.6. NMR spectroscopic analysis

The CPC fractions were also analysed by ¹H NMR to obtain a quantitative aspect of the molecules in the mixtures and co-analysed with the results of the previous profiling methods. NMR was intensively used for the structure elucidation of isolated compound using an array of 1D and 2D homo- and hetero-nuclear NMR experiments [¹H NMR, COSY (Homonuclear Correlation Spectroscopy), HSQC-DEPT (Heteronuclear Single Quantum Correlation spectroscopy) and HMBC (Heteronuclear Multiple Bond Correlation spectroscopy)]. The analysis was performed on a 600 MHz on a Bruker Avance AVIII spectrometer (Bruker Biospin GmbH, Rheinstetten, Germany) equipped with a 5-mm PABBI 1H/D-BB inverse detection probe with a z-gradient. All ¹H NMR spectra were acquired with 128 or 64 scans at 305 K, while certain samples were analyzed using 1D NOESY pulse sequence with water suppression (Bruker's pulse program noesygppr1d). ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were acquired at 600.113 MHz and 150.91 MHz, respectively. For 1D and 2D NMR experiments, 1–10 mg of isolated compounds were dissolved in 600 µL of deuterated methanol (MeOD) and then inserted into NMR tubes. Temperature was controlled by a BVT-3000 digital controller with gas flow 535 L/h. Before each sample set session a standard operation procedure was followed including temperature calibration at 305.0 K. Icon-NMR software v.4.2.6 for TopSpin 2.1, controlling a B-ACS 60-position auto sampler, was used for full automated NMR operation, i. e. temperature control, sample loading, tuning and matching, shimming, lockphase optimization, 90° pulse calibration, data recording and processing (Fourier transformation, phase and baseline correction, chemical shift scale calibration by referencing to the TMS resonance at 0.00 ppm). The spectral width was 14 ppm. Chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm while coupling constants (*J*) in Hz. ¹H and ¹³C shifts were referenced to the residual signal of methanol-d₄ at 3.31 ppm and 49.15 ppm, respectively.

Evaluation of the spectra was carried out using MestreNova 6.1.1 software and TopSpin software version 3.5 pl 1 (Bruker BioSpin GmbH, Germany). Manual phase and baseline correction was applied to all spectra. The multiplicity of vertices is expressed as s (singlet), brs (broad singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), dd (doublet of doublets) and m (multiplet). After acquiring the spectra, the NMR samples were evaporated to dryness under an N₂ flow and subsequently stored in a freezer at –80 °C.

2.3.7. Structure elucidation workflow of isolated metabolites

Initially, ¹H NMR spectra in parallel to LC–HRMS and HPLC–UV/ELSD chromatograms were investigated to assess the purity of the CPC fractions and whether secondary purification should be performed. Subsequently, the strategy to achieve the accurate identification of compounds was based on the HRMS and HRMS/MS data and NMR data interpretation. The putative identification by HRMS was based on different spectrometric and chromatographic features i.e. accurate mass of the pseudomolecular ion, proposed elemental composition, retention time, isotopic pattern, RDBeq. values, fragmentation patterns and by database searching as well as comparison with existing reference standards when available. The databases (DB) used were: *E. coli* Metabolome DB (<http://www.ecmdb.ca/>), METLIN Metabolomics DB (<https://metlin.scripps.edu/>), Human Metabolome DB (HMDB) (<http://www.hmdb.ca/>), ChemSpider chemical structure DB (<http://www.chemspider.com/>), European MassBank DB (<https://massbank.eu/MassBank/>). Identification criteria for LC–HRMS assignment were established as follows: (a) maximum mass deviation of ± 5 ppm between theoretical and measured parent ions, (b) product ions must not exceed the

maximum mass deviation of ± 10 ppm. For structural identification of the isolated metabolites 1D and 2D homo- and heteronuclear NMR experiments (COSY, HSQC and HMBC) were acquired. The observed peaks from NMR spectra were DB queried (HMDB, BMRB <https://bmr.io/>, NP-MRD <https://np-mrd.org/>, Reaxys DB; <https://www.reaxys.com/>), or compared with those previously reported in literature.

3. Results and discussion

Significant advances in synthetic biology the recent years have enabled the development of microbial cell factories with improved production capabilities and potential applications in various fields including pharmaceuticals, biofuels, cosmetics and food additives. Engineered *E. coli* strains (also referred to as *E. coli* biofactories) offer a versatile platform for the production of several valuable compounds, offering significant advantages over their extraction from natural sources or their chemical-enzymatic synthesis. However, although numerous biotechnological approaches have been proposed towards optimization of yield and recovery of compounds of interest these biotechnological methods present drawbacks during extraction, separation, and purification. Especially outside a laboratory environment and towards high or even pilot scale production serious constraints affect the efficacious recovery, yield and purity. To address these challenges, a combination of efficient extraction and purification methods, and thorough process optimization is required.

Based on the above, in the present study we aimed to develop a comprehensive methodology for the production, extraction, purification, and identification of HT and metabolite derivatives from metabolically engineered *E. coli* biofactories. A schematic representation is given in Fig. 1. Apart from chromatographic and analytical methods that are commonly utilized in such studies, our goal was to introduce two liquid–liquid techniques both based on centrifugation for extraction and separation. More specifically, in the current workflow, an ACE extraction process has been hyphenated at-line with stepwise gradient CPC fractionation followed by a prep-HPLC purification step, aiming to isolate HT and other important metabolic derivatives (intermediates and end-products) from the fermentation broth. The preparative isolation of metabolites from the l-DOPA engineered pathway and the unambiguous structural elucidation by HRMS/MS and NMR methods could significantly contribute to the monitoring and validation of the pathway. Through this we can address important hurdles that can arise such as the metabolic burden due to accumulation of intermediates and unwanted byproducts which can inhibit key enzymes or cell viability.

3.1. Extraction

Several processes, mainly developed for laboratory-scale analytical and quality control purposes are available for the extraction of the phenolic compounds from different matrices or media, such as solid-phase extraction, liquid-liquid extraction, ultrasound assisted extraction, centrifugal partition extraction, etc. [45,46]. However, the recovery of bioactive phenolic compounds from large volumes of fermentation broths implies specific constraints and requires the development of a suitable extraction process, which will achieve high extraction yield, high recovery with low solvent consumption and operational reproducibility [47]. The working principles of ACE provide several advantages for HT extraction, including improved mass transfer between the liquid phases [48], rapid phase separation [49], continuous processing [39] minimizing the extraction time, and thus making the process more cost-effective and scalable. Additionally, due to its reduced solvent consumption and energy efficiency, it is considered as a technique with low environmental footprint [50]. Despite its advantages, ACE is highly underutilized for the extraction of active components in biotechnology, but also in the field of food and foods products. Specifically, only a handful of reports are available for the efficient pilot-scale extraction of biophenols and specifically from extra virgin olive oil by

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the whole procedure for the production, extraction, isolation, purification and *de novo* structural elucidation of HT metabolites and other intermediate compounds.

Angelis et al. [51], lignans from sesame oil by Michailidis et al. [52], for phenolic compounds from olive mill wastewater by J.-Q. Xu et al. [53], as well as caffeine from natural sources by W. Duan et al. [39]. To our knowledge there is no prior information related to the treatment of cell culture media in biotechnology workflows.

In our study, the fraction of phenolic compounds was extracted from the fermentation broth using a pilot-scale ACE BXP190 system in a single-stage process. Ethyl acetate (EtOAc) was chosen as the extraction solvent due to its effectiveness in isolating the target compound, its immiscibility with the aqueous fermentation solution, and its high volatility, which facilitates rapid evaporation and reuse with minimal energy and time requirements. These properties make EtOAc highly suitable for industrial applications. Additionally, EtOAc has been widely used for liquid-liquid extraction of biophenols from natural products, demonstrating its ability to extract compounds across a broad range of polarities and achieve high enrichment factors [54].

Laboratory experimental trials for the recovery of HT from fermentation broth concluded that the optimal rotation speed of ACE's inner basket is 3400 rpm. The optimum flow rate was determined at 3 mL/min for each phase. Two key factors were taken into consideration to scale up the procedure on pilot level, the applied Relative Centrifugal Force (RCF) on the emulsified biphasic system and the residence time of the system in it. To determine the first factor (RCF) the following equation was used.

$$RCF = 1.12 \times radius \times \left(\frac{rpm}{1000} \right)^2$$

The laboratory scale ACE (BXP012) has a radius of 6 mm, while pilot scale (BXP190) has a radius of 85 mm. Firstly, the RCF of the laboratory experiment was calculated and afterwards the same value was applied in the equation while the radius was changed from 6 to 85 mm, to determine the corresponding rpm for pilot scale apparatus. To ensure a consistent residence time under centrifugal forces, the flow rate was adjusted based on the volume of the inner basket. The inner basket of BXP012 has a volume of 2.2 mL and the flow rate was 3 mL/min for each phase, meaning that the emulsified biphasic system remained for ~0.7 min under G force field. The inner basket of BXP190 has a volume of 4.2

L. To maintain the same residence time at the pilot scale process, the flow rate was adjusted to 6 L/min per phase.

Afterwards, the first step of the pilot extraction was the separate preparation of the two phases of solvent system: 100 L of the feed aqueous phase (fermentation broth) and 100 L of the organic phase composed of distilled EtOAc, and then the extraction procedure started by pumping the heavy phase at a flow rate of 8 L/min and at the rotation speed of 900 rpm. When the heavy phase came out from the extractor, its flow rate decreased at 6 L/min and the light phase was pumped with the same flow (6 L/min), while the rotation speed was maintained at 1050 rpm. The extraction procedure lasted 40 min and finally 100 L of treated aqueous phase and the same volume of enriched in biophenols organic phase were separately collected into two different barrels. The extract was initially concentrated in a pilot-scale rotary evaporator of 20 L (Buchi), under vacuum at 4 °C and then, after reducing the volume of the extract, it was transferred to a lab-scale rotary evaporator, where the extract was concentrated to dryness. The concentrated EtOAc was reused in two more extraction cycles, giving a total final extract weight of 68.83 g. From the extraction performed the extract yield was calculated at 688.3 mg/L of fermentation broth.

3.2. Isolation and purification

Following extraction, the recovered phenolic fraction was subjected to CPC separation. In addition to the already mentioned advantages to other separation techniques, one of the most critical aspects for the particular application of CPC is the use of liquid stationary phase, eliminating issues like column fouling, irreversible adsorption, or degradation of the stationary phase. Moreover, another important aspect is its higher column capacity which allows the processing of larger volumes of fermentation broth without compromising separation efficiency, the scalability from laboratory to pilot scale operations, the reduced risk of sample loss and the compatibility with complex fermentation broths without significant pre-treatment [40,55–57]. In some recent studies [47,51,58,59], high performance CPC has been successfully applied for the isolation of HT and its more complex derivatives such as oleacein, oleocanthal and other valuable biophenols

from olive oil. In the last decades, its application is rapidly growing for separation purposes however there is no published report to our knowledge for its employment in biotechnological materials.

As a starting point for separation and in order to conclude for the optimum solvent system for the isolation of individual phenolics from the *E. coli* biofactories, 10 sets of biphasic systems consisting of *c*-hexane or *n*-hept, EtOAc, MeOH or isoProp and H₂O (also known as the Arizona system) were selected and partition coefficient factors (K_D) were evaluated (analytical description in Supporting Information). The Arizona system is a versatile and highly reported solvent system for the isolation and purification of compounds from complex mixtures e.g. natural extracts, due to its wide range of polarities that can be covered [41,60]. Arizona system can be modified to favor the partitioning of more polar compounds as in the case of HT and its metabolites by replacing the alcohol component of the solvent system with propanol or butanol [60]. Interestingly, butanol is a major organic phase modifier which can facilitate the partitioning of rather polar molecules [41,61]. Although efficient, this solvent system was rejected in our study due to the difficulty of evaporation, which would make the process time-consuming. After evaluation of all tested systems by HPLC-DAD and K_D factors the biphasic system *c*-Hex/EtOAc/MeOH/H₂O in proportion 1:9:2:8 (v/v/v/v) was selected for the separation. Detailed information about the evaluation of the biphasic solvent systems and the conditions during CPC experiment can be found in Tables S1 and S2 in Supporting Information.

All the obtained fractions after CPC application were subjected in parallel to HPLC-DAD/ELSD, UPLC-HRMS and ¹H NMR analysis extrapolating and combining the strengths of each method. The profiling was followed by a second orthogonal separation step to the enriched in HT and derivatives fraction via prep-RP-HPLC or in cases of minor components by preparative TLC. By utilizing orthogonal separation mechanism, where each dimension operates on distinct principles i.e. liquid-liquid and solid-liquid, the separation selectivity and peak capacity are enhanced enabling more precise and efficient purification of target metabolites. This 2D separation approach is proved to be a highly effective strategy for separating and purifying structurally similar compounds from complex mixtures [62–64].

3.3. Identification of metabolites

After purification procedure, 23 compounds were isolated in total and unambiguously identified using LC-HRMS/MS as well as 1 and 2D NMR (Table S5, Supporting Information). The capacity of the applied workflow to treat high quantities of material in a reasonable time allowed the isolation of target compounds but also of minor molecules. Also, the isolation yield of purified compounds (Table S3, Supporting Information) enabled the implementation of spectroscopic methods i.e. NMR which is not possible in typical workflows due to sensitivity constraints. In more detail, the isolated and identified compounds belong to diverse chemical groups. They belong to phenolic acids, phenylalcohols, diketopiperazines, hydroxybenzaldehydes, phenolic esters and nitrobenzenes. Of these, 16 are metabolites of HT found in the biochemical pathway of tyrosine (precursor molecules and metabolic derivatives), two HT dimers, one of which is described for the first time in the literature, a cyclodipeptide, two chloroamphenicol metabolites (antibiotic), as well as two structurally unique compounds were isolated and for the first time are correlated to the tyrosine pathway.

During the isolation procedure some compounds were obtained directly from CPC separation process in satisfactory purity (>90 %) and others through preparative HPLC or TLC analysis for purity enhancement. The two main expected metabolites HT (1) and tyrosol (3) were isolated from sub-fractions 5_a and 7_a, respectively. The ESI(–)-HRMS spectrum of subfraction fr5_a showed a pseudomolecular ion [$M - H$][–] at m/z 153.0552 with a suggested Elemental Composition (EC) of C₈H₉O₃ and RDB_{eq} of 4. From the ¹H NMR spectrum an ABX spin system corresponding to a catechol was observed comprised of a doublet (d) at δ

6.70 (1H, $J = 8.06$ Hz) (H-5), a d at δ 6.67 (1H, $J = 2.06$ Hz) (H-2) and a double of doublets (dd) at δ 6.55 (H, $J = 2.06/8.06$ Hz) (H-6) as well as two triplets (t) of the aliphatic chain at δ 3.69 (2H) and δ 2.68 (2H). Accordingly, the structure elucidation of the structurally similar tyrosol is described in the supplementary material (Fig. S4–6 & S12–16).

In a less polar fraction and specifically at the subfraction 8_a HT acetate (2) was isolated as a colorless oil corresponding to the peak at t_R 4.74 min in the LC-MS chromatograms (Fig. S11, Supporting Information) and a pseudomolecular ion at m/z 195.0667 in the ESI(–)-HRMS spectrum. The high-resolution ESI-MS (negative mode) led, in conjunction with its ¹³C NMR data, to the molecular formula C₁₀H₁₂O₄. LC-MS/MS analysis gave the main diagnostic fragment ion at m/z 135.0456. The presence of a catechol moiety is again evident (ABX spin system) with d at δ 6.69 (1H, $J = 8.15$ Hz) (H-5), a d at δ 6.67 (1H, $J = 2.02$ Hz) (H-2) and a dd at δ 6.55 (H, $J = 2.02/8.15$ Hz) (H-6) as well as three resonances at δ 4.21 ppm (2H, t), 2.79 ppm (2H, t) and 2.01 (s, 3H) corresponding to the signals of the aliphatic chain. Further analysis of 2D-NMR spectra (COSY, HSQC-DEPT, HMBC) verified the structure of the isolated compound (Fig.S7–10, Supporting Information), which was consistent with previously reported data [65]. Hydroxytyrosol acetate is a typical metabolite detected in human or animal biofluids after HT supplementation [66–68]. Studies utilizing *in vivo* [69] and *in vitro* [70] models have shown that 2 is more effective than HT in inhibiting platelet aggregation triggered by ADP, collagen, or arachidonic acid, and it also enhances nitric oxide production [71]. Its efficacy in this regard is comparable to that of acetylsalicylic acid and recently has been suggested as possible incorporation in dietary supplements due to better hydrophilic/lipophilic balance [72]. In another study, González-Correa et al., [73] reported its neuroprotective effect (and HT) in rat brain slices subjected to hypoxia–reoxygenation, while Sánchez-Fidalgo et al., described the anti-inflammatory effect on acute ulcerative colitis [74] (Fig. 2).

Tyrosol acetate (4), 4-hydroxyphenyl acetate (5), and 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (6) were isolated from the fr10 after secondary purification with preparative-HPLC. The ESI(–)-HRMS spectrum of 4 corresponded to the peak at t_R 7.37 min showed a pseudomolecular ion [$M - H$][–] at m/z 179.0716 with a suggested EC of C₁₁H₁₁O₃ and RDB_{eq} of 5. The presence of a tyrosol moiety is evident by the existence of two d peaks at 7.04 ppm and 6.71 ppm (2H each, $J = 8.7$ Hz) as well as three resonances at 4.19 ppm (2H, t), 2.82 ppm (2H, t) and 2.00 (3H, s) corresponding to protons of two methylene and a methyl groups (Fig. S17–20, Supporting Information). Regarding 5, its pseudomolecular ion [$M - H$][–] of m/z 151.0403 was detected in the HRMS spectrum with the suggested EC of C₈H₇O₃ and it was in agreement with previously reported data [75]. Additionally, the HRMS/MS spectrum gave the characteristic diagnostic fragment ion at m/z 123.0452. The ¹H NMR spectrum also confirmed the structure from the characteristic resonances at δ 7.08 ppm (2H, d, $J = 8.46$ Hz) and 6.75 ppm (2H, d, $J = 8.46$ Hz) corresponding to a para-aromatic ring substitution and a singlet (s) at 2.16 ppm (3H, s) indicative for a methyl group of an acetic moiety and it was in agreement with previously reported data [76]. Regarding compound 6, purified by the subfraction 10_d showed a peak at t_R 2.88 min in the LC-MS chromatograms (Fig. S27, Supporting Information) and the pseudomolecular ion at m/z 137.0240 in the ESI(–)-HRMS spectrum and the characteristic fragment ion at m/z 93.0345. From the analysis of the ¹H NMR spectrum, the structure of the molecule was confirmed, with the characteristic two d peaks at 7.88 ppm and 6.81 ppm (2H each, $J = 8.77$ Hz). The overall structure assignment including 2D NMR analysis for all three metabolites is presented in the Supporting Information (S17–20, S26–29). 4-hydroxyphenyl acetate and 4-hydroxybenzoic acid exist in all living organisms, ranging from bacteria to humans. 4-hydroxybenzoic acid is a key intermediate in the biosynthesis of ubiquinones in all living organisms [77]. It can be biosynthesized by the enzyme Chorismate lyase that transforms chorismate into 4-hydroxybenzoate and pyruvate. This enzyme catalyses the first step in ubiquinone biosynthesis in *E. coli* [77].

Fig. 2. Chemical structures of hydroxytyrosol (1), hydroxytyrosol acetate (2), tyrosol (3), tyrosol acetate (4), 4-hydroxyphenyl acetate (5), 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (6).

Investigating further the fractions and subfractions and specifically Fr5, a peak was detected during the LC-MS analysis with interesting spectrometric characteristics. Further purification led to subfraction 5_b and the identification of **3-Hydroxy-4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-butanone (7)**. During its ESI(-)-HRMS analysis a pseudomolecular ion $[M - H]^-$ at m/z 195.0660 with a suggested EC of C₉H₁₁O₄ and RDB_{eq} of 5, was detected. At the HRMS/MS spectra the main fragments at m/z 123.0451 indicated the presence of 1-methylcatechol moiety and 1-propylcatechol moiety (m/z 151.0404). Also, the fragments at m/z 109.0296 and 177.0560 indicated the loss of 3-hydroxy-2-butanone moiety and H₂O, respectively (Fig. S34, Supporting Information). The ¹H NMR spectrum showed the presence of seven peaks of which three correspond to the proton signals of a catechol moiety [a d at δ 6.69 (1H, $J = 2.06$ Hz, H-2), a d at δ 6.67 (1H, $J = 8.07$ Hz, H-5) and a dd at δ 6.65 (1H, $J = 2.06/8.07$ Hz, H-6)]. The remaining four peaks were identified as a 3-Hydroxy-2-butanone moiety [dd at δ 4.24 (1H, $J = 4.94/7.96$ Hz, H-3') two dd at δ 2.88 and 2.70 (H-4'a/4'b), and s at δ 2.13 (3H, H-1') of the methyl group]. Further study of 2D-NMR spectra verified the

structure. For instance, COSY correlations between H-3' and the protons of the methylene moiety H-4'a and H-4'b indicated the hydroxyl substitution on C-3'. Moreover, the HMBC correlation between H-4'a, H-4'b and H-3' with C-1 confirmed the position of the side chain on the basic scaffold. The complete 2D NMR data of 3-Hydroxy-4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-butanone are presented in Fig. S30-S33 (Supporting Information).

Compound 7, is a methyl ketone derivative of salviamic acid or danshensu which is a characteristic compound of *Salvia miltiorrhiza*, a well-known medicinal plant in Chinese traditional medicine (TCM) [78]. Its *R* isomer regarding the chiral center C-3' is abundant in natural sources and has been investigated for numerous biological properties [79]. Moreover, its *S* isomer has been also synthesized. Interestingly, several attempts to produce 7 biotechnologically have been reported due to its low concentration in plant material and the array of health benefits [79,80]. Despite that 7 has been registered as a chemical entity it was not possible to trace accurate spectroscopic or spectrometric data (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. ¹H NMR spectrum of 3-Hydroxy-4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-butanone (7), in d₄-MeOH.

Structurally similar to **7** was compound **8** which was isolated from the subfraction 8_c and was identified as **3-Hydroxy-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)butan-2-one**, the respective butanone derivative of tyrosol. The spectroscopic data was much like **7** with the only difference in the presence of an AAB spin system instead of ABX (δ 7.06 (2H, J = 8.46 Hz) and δ 6.70 (2H, J = 8.46 Hz). The ESI(-)-HRMS analysis confirmed the structure showing a $[M - H]^-$ at m/z 179.07161 with a suggested EC of C₁₀H₁₁O₃ and RDB_{eq} of 5. These data and 2D NMR analysis (Supporting Information, Fig. S40-S44), was consistent with previously reported data [81]. This metabolite was first isolated and elucidated by Peng et al., from halotolerant marine fungal strain *Wallemia sebi* PXP-89 [82]

Compounds **9**, **10**, **11**, **12**, **13** and **14** which are also tyrosol and HT derivatives have been also isolated from the CPC fractions. They are expected components since they are obtained via the biochemical pathway engineered from l-tyrosine to HT through dopamine (L-DOPA) pathway. The occurrence of all these metabolites and HT derivatives, their formation and their association as components of metabolism cycles is well described in the literature under catecholamine biosynthesis (Fig. 4).

Two interesting compounds were isolated and presented separately since they comprise dimeric forms of HT. It is well known that HT is prone to autooxidation forming dimers and/or polymers. However, the mechanism underlined behind this reaction is different according to the substrate and the conditions e.g. chemical or enzymatic environment while there is not much information in the literature regarding the accurate structure of such dimers.

The first dimer, was identified as **1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)isochroman-6,7-diol (15)** isolated from subfraction fr9_d as pale yellow solid and specifically it is a homodimer of HT implying the participation of two catechol moieties. In ESI(-)-HRMS spectrum an $[M - H]^-$ at m/z 273.0765 was detected, with a suggested EC of C₁₅H₁₃O₅ and nine degrees of unsaturation. In the ¹H NMR spectrum a total of ten peaks were detected. As previously in other HT derivatives the resonances of the ABX spin system were observed together with 3 singlets, and two sets of peaks corresponding to two methylene groups. More specifically, from HSQC and HMBC correlations it is evident that the two s peaks correspond to aromatic protons (H-6/C-6, 6.65/115.74 ppm, respectively) and the third one to an oxymethine (H-1/C-1, 5.45/80.58 ppm, respectively). Similarly, an oxymethylene (H-3a/3b, C-3 at 64.64 ppm) together with a methylene participating in an extra ring (H-4a/4b, C-4 at 29.05 ppm) were observed. Furthermore, the HMBC correlations of H-3a/C-4, H-3a/C-1, H-3a/C-10, and H-4a/C-10 verified the structural motif of an isochroman. More information is given to Supporting

Information (Fig. S55–59). Compound **15** has been previously isolated by Y.-M. Yan et al. [83] from the ethanol extract of *Blaps japonensis* (Tenebrionidae) also known as the stink beetle. It is a well recognized medicinal insect of TCM that has been used to treat inflammation, infection, and cancer. Moreover, a methylated derivative of **15** has been reported in extra-virgin olive oil by Bianco et al., [84,85] while it has been synthesized by Lorenz et al., [86] by acid-catalyzed oxa-Pictet-Spengler reaction [87]. Therefore, a hypothesis could be made that **15** is formed through l-Dopa pathway in *E.coli*, by condensation of HT and protocatechuic aldehyde (Fig. S60, Supporting Information), similarly to the formation of olive isochromans during malaxation in the olive oil production process [88,89] (Fig. 5).

Another metabolite with similar chemical behavior to **15** was isolated from fr9 and specifically subfraction 9_c and was obtained as a light-yellow powder. Its molecular formula was obtained by ESI-HRMS as C₁₆H₁₄O₆ with $[M-H]^-$ at m/z 301.0714. A simple comparison with the NMR data of **15** showed high similarity indicating another HT dimer. Signals corresponding to a typical ABX spin system and two singlets of the second phenyl group as in the case of **15** were also present. However, additional resonances implied the presence of an extra ring other than isochroman. Very informative for the assignment were the HSQC and HMBC spectra, indicating 16 carbons, including an oxymethylene, an oxymethine, a methylene and a carbonyl group indicating a seven-membered ring. Further study of 2D-NMR spectra verified this theory through COSY correlations for instance (H-16/H-17, H13/H1), as well as HMBC correlations between H-1/C-12 H-1/C-11 H-7/C-2, H-1/C-6 and H-1/C-10 which indicated the substitution pattern. Complete interpretation of NMR spectra is given in Fig. 6. Thus, metabolite **16** was identified as **1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-7,8-dihydroxy-4,5-dihydrobenzo[d]oxepin-2(1H)-one**. This is the first report of this structure in literature and in our opinion is a novel dimer of HT. Chemically it could be classified as ω -lactone and not isochromane. However, a similar conjugation reaction as for the formation of **15** cannot be disregarded.

In HRMS full scan spectrum (Fig. 6, B) the deprotonated ion (pseudomolecule ion) of **16** is detected together with several adduct ions with H₂O, formic acid (FA) used in the mobile phase, chlorine as well as with the in source dimer adduct $[2M-H]^-$. In the MS/MS level several fragments are observed corresponding to the loss of different species and specifically CH₂O, CO₂ and C₂H₂O₂. Also, in low masses, ions corresponding to HT related fragments are detected (Fig. 6, C).

Another interesting compound that was isolated from the fermentation broth was **Cyclo-(Pro-Tyr) (17)** or **maculosin**. Even though it doesn't belong to HT relevant metabolites, it is worth mentioning due to its appealing biological properties. It is a cyclodipeptide obtained by the

Fig. 4. Chemical structures of protocatechuic aldehyde (9), 3,4-dihydroxyphenylacetic acid (10), homovanillyl alcohol (11), 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (12), 4-hydroxyphenylacetic acid (13), 1-(4-hydroxyphenyl)butane-2,3-diol (14).

Fig. 5. A) ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-(3,4-hydroxyphenyl)isochroman-6,7-diol, 15 in MeOH-d_4 . B) HRMS spectrum of 15 where $[\text{M-H}]^-$ is highlighted (ESI-). C) HRMS/MS spectrum of 15 (CID 35 V). The main fragment ions are highlighted.

condensation of proline and tyrosine amino acids [90]. Cyclo-(Pro-Tyr) was obtained as a white amorphous powder, and based on LC–HRMS analysis the molecular formula was determined $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (m/z 261.1231) corresponding to $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ ion and RDBEq. of 7. The ^1H NMR spectrum showed the presence of tyrosine moiety with the characteristic para-aromatic ring substitution as indicated by the two doublets at δ 7.04 (2H, $J = 8.55$ Hz) and δ 6.71 (2H, $J = 8.55$ Hz) as well as the two dd at 3.04 and 3.08 ppm corresponding to the methylene protons of C-10. Moreover, ^1H NMR signals and chemical shift of H-3 and H-6 and the presence of two carbonyl groups (C-1, 170.59 ppm, C-4, 167.15 ppm) highlighted a diketopiperazine structure. COSY correlations between the H-6, H-7, H-8, and H-9 protons established the presence of an alkyl

chain. This chain was connected to a carbonyl function based on an HMBC correlation between H-7 and C-1 indicating a proline group. COSY correlations between H-10 and H-3 (3.06 ppm and 4.36 ppm) and HMBC correlations between H-10 and C-3 (2J) and C-4 (3J) denoted the position of the linkage between the aromatic ring and the diketopiperazine moiety (Supporting Information, Fig. S61–65). These dipeptides are not only abundant in nature but are often produced as degradation products of polypeptides, especially in processed food and beverages. Maculosin occurs in numerous natural materials from fungi, bacteria, plants to mammals, often alone or embedded in more complex structures. The wide spectrum of their biological properties points to various therapeutic possibilities [91] Maculosin has been isolated from other

Fig. 6. A) ¹H NMR spectrum of 1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-7,8-dihydroxy-4,5-dihydrobenzo[d]oxepin-2(1H)-one, 16, in MeOH-d₄. B) HRMS spectrum of 16. C) HRMS/MS spectrum of 16 (CID 35 V). The main fragment ions are highlighted.

Fig. 7. 2D NMR spectra of 16 in (MeOH-d₄), A) COSY, B) HSQC, C) HMBC; COSY (red arrows, H—H, ³J) and HMBC (blue arrows, C—H, ²J-³J) cross-peaks correlations are given.

Fig. 8. Chemical structure of maculosin (17).

microbial strains and it is referred as a host-specific phytotoxin produced by the fungal pathogen *Alternaria alternata* on spotted knapweed (*Centaurea maculosa*) [92–95]. Together with the above-mentioned compounds, other molecules like glucose and acetyl phosphate, both expected to be present in the broth, were isolated and identified. Also, metabolites of the antibiotic chloraphenicol (mono- and diacetate) which are also expected in the treated material, were also recovered and more insight is given in the Supporting Information (Fig. S66–75).

3.4. Enrichment of the DOPA microbial metabolic pathway

As mentioned already, *E. coli* stands out as a promising microbial host for the heterologous production of bioactive molecules and a wide range of metabolic engineering techniques and approaches have emerged, utilizing *E. coli* biofactories [96]. The efficient application of microbial cells to produce chemicals often requires modification of the

microbial metabolism redirecting the primary metabolic flow from glucose to varying branches of its metabolism [97]. Especially when heterologous genes are expressed the redirection of the flow is expected to produce a new array of metabolites. Tyrosine is an essential aromatic amino acid that essentially is required for protein biosynthesis and is synthesized *de-novo* in bacteria. Apart from this, tyrosine is involved in numerous biochemical pathways to support primary metabolism through the synthesis of various tyrosine-derived metabolites. When ECMDDB is queried with the term “tyrosine”, it returns to nine pathways where tyrosine is involved, leading to an analogue number of tyrosine-metabolites. Consequently, the *E. coli* chassis consists of enzymes that produce tyrosine and various tyrosine-derived metabolites that load the bacterial cytoplasm. On the other hand, there aren't enzymes characterized to produce DOPA. 4-Hydroxyphenylacetate 3-monooxygenase (*HpaB*) is a native *E. coli* enzyme that upon complement with the NAD(P)H-flavin oxidoreductase (*HpaC*), produce 3,4 dihydroxyphenylacetic [98]. *HpaB* put in line with *HpaC* (*HpaBC*) can also act on tyrosine to give DOPA, though with much lower activity [30, 99]. That is why DOPA is not traced on non-engineered strains of *E. coli*. In this study, l-DOPA or DOPA served as a precursor molecule for the biosynthesis of HT. Because of the structure similarity of tyrosine and DOPA (DOPA is an ortho-hydroxylated derivative of tyrosine), it is expected the plethora of tyrosine metabolites to extend also to DOPA-metabolites.

In a previous study by our groups, the objective was to monitor the biochemical pathway of HT synthesis by detecting and quantifying key molecules to optimize the procedure [28]. In the current work, in addition to introducing a new method for extracting biotechnological media and separating metabolites, we aimed not only to verify the proposed pathway but also to uncover new HT metabolites. In Fig. 9 the entire pathway is briefly presented. Both the genetically modified tyrosine pathway (A) from glucose to tyrosine and the heterologous

Fig. 9. Proposed biotransformation pathway of HT in metabolically engineered *E. coli* biofactory. Gene-respective enzyme abbreviations: AAS, aromatic acetaldehyde synthase. ALR, aldehyde reductase. AroA, 5-enolpyruvoylshikimate 3-phosphate synthase. AroB, dehydroquinone synthase. AroC, chorismate synthase. AroD, dehydroquinone dehydratase. AroE, shikimate dehydrogenase. AroG, 3-deoxy-D-arabino-heptulosonate synthase. AroL, shikimate kinase. DDC, DOPA decarboxylase. feaB, phenylacetaldehyde dehydrogenase, MAO, monoamine oxidase. PpsA, phosphoenolpyruvate synthase. TDC, tyrosine decarboxylase. TktA, transketolase A. TYR, tyrosinase. TyrA, chorismate mutase/prephenate dehydrogenase. TyrB, tyrosine aminotransferase. YdiB, quininate, shikimate dehydrogenase. In colored boxes the isolated metabolites are highlighted.

pathway of HT synthesis (B) are schematically represented. With the proposed methodology it was possible to isolate 16 HT metabolites found in the biochemical pathway of tyrosine (precursor molecules and metabolic derivatives) which are highlighted in colored boxes. It is important to note here that the identification was carried out with HRMS/MS but also NMR which led to high confidence structure elucidation. This is of high importance in order to assist the evaluation and optimization of the biosynthetic route applied. This is one of the major advantages of the proposed workflow since several inconsistencies and vague identifications could be found in the literature comprising a critical obstacle to rational design or even interpretation of data. Thus, based on our results, it became possible to enrich the initial and theoretical pathway of HT biosynthesis from tyrosine.

4. Conclusion

The current study presents a comprehensive and innovative methodology for the biotechnological production, extraction, purification, and structural elucidation of HT and its metabolites using metabolically engineered *E. coli* biofactories. By integrating liquid-liquid centrifugal techniques i.e. ACE and CPC we have developed a streamlined and scalable workflow that addresses the challenges associated with the downstream processing of biotechnologically produced HT. The proposed methodology could be an efficient alternative to isolation or chemical synthesis of HT and/or its metabolites making the process more cost-effective, environmentally friendly, faster and scalable.

To our knowledge and despite their several advantages, such techniques haven't been employed before for the treatment of biotechnological materials. Furthermore, the centrifugal techniques are

complimented by conventional solid-liquid separations methods establishing when needed 2D-separations highly suitable for minor compounds and/or high purity isolation. Among this line, the proposed workflow allows the structure elucidation of the isolated compounds with NMR spectroscopy enabling the unambiguous identification of metabolites. This is of particular importance since the precise structure elucidation of metabolites is questionable when only spectrometric (MS) methods are used.

Employing the proposed workflow, it was possible to isolate and identify 23 compounds from the *E. coli* cellular broth, with 16 belonging to the heterologous biosynthetic route of HT synthesis from tyrosine through L-Dopa. Thus, it was possible to enrich drastically the theoretical synthetic puzzle of biotransformation occurred in the *E. coli* biofactories. This facilitates the monitoring and optimization of metabolic flux, addressing issues such as metabolic burden and the accumulation of inhibitory byproducts. Finally, the proposed workflow could be utilized for the treatment of any biotechnological material for the isolation of bioactive compounds or compounds of interest with diverse properties and applications. We strongly believe that centrifugal chromatographic techniques are highly underutilized in biotechnology and deserve greater attention for their multiple advantages at various scales.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evangelos Kalampokis: Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Theodora Nikou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Efthymia Panteli:** Investigation, Data curation. **Dimitris Michailidis:** Methodology, Investigation. **Emmanouil Trantas:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Filippos Ververidis:** Writing –

review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Maria Halabalaki:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2025.466103](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2025.466103).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- M.A. Carluccio, L. Siculella, M.A. Ancora, M. Massaro, E. Scoditti, C. Storelli, F. Visioli, A. Distante, R. De Caterina, Olive oil and red wine antioxidant polyphenols inhibit endothelial activation: antiatherogenic properties of Mediterranean diet phytochemicals, *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* 23 (2003) 622–629, <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.ATV.0000062884.69432.A0>.
- X. Li, Z. Chen, Y. Wu, Y. Yan, X. Sun, Q. Yuan, Establishing an artificial pathway for efficient biosynthesis of hydroxytyrosol, *ACS Synth. Biol.* 7 (2018) 647–654, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssynbio.7b00385>.
- F. Visioli, G. Bellomo, C. Galli, Free radical-scavenging properties of olive oil polyphenols, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 247 (1998) 60–64, <https://doi.org/10.1006/bbrc.1998.8735>.
- P. Rodríguez-López, J. Lozano-Sánchez, I. Borrás-Linares, T. Emanuelli, J. A. Menéndez, A. Segura-Carretero, Structure–biological activity relationships of extra-virgin olive oil phenolic compounds: health properties and bioavailability, *Antioxidants* 9 (2020) 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9080685>.
- Y.V. Simos, S. Zerikiotis, P. Lekkas, C. Zachariou, M. Halabalaki, F. Ververidis, E. A. Trantas, K. Tsamis, D. Peschos, C. Angelidis, et al., Hydroxytyrosol produced by engineered *Escherichia coli* strains activates Nrf2/HO-1 pathway: an in vitro and in vivo study, *Exp. Biol. Med.* 248 (2023) 1598–1612, <https://doi.org/10.1177/15353702231187647>.
- A.K. Marković, J. Torić, M. Barbarić, C.J. Brala, Hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol and derivatives and their potential effects on human health, *Molecules* 24 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24102001>.
- J. Rodríguez-Morató, A. Boronat, A. Kotronoulas, M. Pujadas, A. Pastor, E. Olesi, C. Pérez-Mañá, O. Khymentis, M. Fitó, M. Farré, et al., Metabolic disposition and biological significance of simple phenols of dietary origin: hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol, *Drug Metab. Rev.* 48 (2016) 218–236, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03602532.2016.1179754>.
- T.A. Wani, F.A. Masoodi, A. Gani, W.N. Baba, N. Rahmanian, R. Akhter, I.A. Wani, M. Ahmad, Olive oil and its principal bioactive compound: hydroxytyrosol – A review of the recent literature, *Trends. Food Sci. Technol.* 77 (2018) 77–90, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2018.05.001>.
- S. D’Angelo, C. Manna, V. Migliardi, O. Mazzoni, P. Morrica, G. Capasso, G. Pontoni, P. Galletti, V. Zappia, Pharmacokinetics and metabolism of hydroxytyrosol, a natural antioxidant from olive oil, *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 29 (2001) 1492–1498.
- S. D’Angelo, C. Manna, V. Migliardi, O. Mazzoni, P. Morrica, G. Capasso, G. Pontoni, P. Galletti, V. Zappia, Pharmacokinetics and metabolism of hydroxytyrosol, a natural antioxidant from olive oil, *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 29 (2001) 1492–1498.
- M. Robles-Almazan, M. Pulido-Moran, J. Moreno-Fernandez, C. Ramirez-Tortosa, C. Rodriguez-Garcia, J.L. Quiles, Mc Ramirez-Tortosa, Hydroxytyrosol: bioavailability, toxicity, and clinical applications, *Food Res. Int.* 105 (2018) 654–667, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.11.053>.
- F. Visioli, A. Poli, C. Galli, Antioxidant and other biological activities of phenols from olives and olive oil, *Med. Res. Rev.* 22 (2002) 65–75, <https://doi.org/10.1002/med.1028>.
- G. Bisignano, A. Tomaino, R.Lo Cascio, G. Crisafi, N. Uccella, A. Saija, On the In-vitro antimicrobial activity of oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.* 51 (2010) 971–974, <https://doi.org/10.1211/0022357991773258>.
- K.L. Tuck, P.J. Hayball, Major phenolic compounds in olive oil: metabolism and health effects, *J. Nutr. Biochem.* 13 (2002) 636–644, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2863\(02\)00229-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2863(02)00229-2).
- J. Britton, R. Davis, K.E. O’Connor, Chemical, physical and biotechnological approaches to the production of the potent antioxidant hydroxytyrosol, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 103 (2019) 5957–5974, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-019-09914-9>.
- X. Sun, X. Li, X. Shen, J. Wang, Q. Yuan, Recent advances in microbial production of phenolic compounds, *Chinese J. Chem. Eng.* 30 (2021) 54–61, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjche.2020.09.001>.
- A.D. Kalampaliki, V. Giannouli, A.L. Skaltsounis, I.K. Kostakis, A three-step, gram-scale synthesis of hydroxytyrosol, hydroxytyrosol acetate, and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylglycol, *Molecules* (2019) 24, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24183239>.
- Z.L. Zhang, J. Chen, Q. Xu, C. Rao, C. Qiao, Efficient synthesis of hydroxytyrosol from 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, *Synth. Commun.* 42 (2012) 794–798, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00397911.2010.531369>.
- S. Azabou, W. Najjar, A. Ghorbel, S. Sayadi, Mild photochemical synthesis of the antioxidant hydroxytyrosol via conversion of tyrosol, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 55 (2007) 4877–4882, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf070081j>.
- Camillo, V.S.; Lellis, D. Convenient synthesis of hydroxytyrosol and its lipophilic derivatives from tyrosol or homovanillyl alcohol. 2008, 2, 8897–8904, [10.1021/jf801558z](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf801558z).
- P. Bovicelli, R. Antonioletti, S. Mancini, S. Casio, G. Borioni, S. Ammendola, M. Barontini, Expedient synthesis of hydroxytyrosol and its esters, *Synth. Commun.* 37 (2007) 4245–4252, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00397910701575509>.
- D. Deffieux, P. Gossart, S. Quideau, Facile and sustainable synthesis of the natural antioxidant hydroxytyrosol, *Tetrahedron. Lett.* 55 (2014) 2455–2458, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tetlet.2014.02.134>.
- P. Ziosi, C. Paolucci, F. Santarelli, T. Tabanelli, S. Passeri, F. Cavani, P. Righi, A two-step process for the synthesis of hydroxytyrosol, *ChemSusChem.* 11 (2018) 2202–2210, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201800684>.
- C. Li, P. Jia, Y. Bai, T.P. Fan, X. Zheng, Y. Cai, Efficient synthesis of hydroxytyrosol from L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine using engineered *Escherichia coli* whole cells, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 67 (2019) 6867–6873, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b01856>.
- D. Chung, S.Y. Kim, J.H. Ahn, Production of three phenylethanoids, tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol, and salidroside, using plant genes expressing in *Escherichia coli*, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017) 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-02042-2>.
- C. Li, P. Jia, Y. Bai, T.P. Fan, X. Zheng, Y. Cai, Efficient synthesis of hydroxytyrosol from L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine using engineered *Escherichia coli* whole cells, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 67 (2019) 6867–6873, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b01856>.
- Y. Satoh, K. Tajima, M. Muneakata, J.D. Keasling, T.S. Lee, Engineering of L-tyrosine oxidation in *Escherichia coli* and microbial production of hydroxytyrosol, *Metab. Eng.* 14 (2012) 603–610, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2012.08.002>.
- E. Trantas, E. Navakoudis, T. Pavlidis, T. Nikou, M. Halabalaki, L. Skaltsounis, Dual pathway for metabolic engineering of *Escherichia coli* to produce the highly valuable hydroxytyrosol, *PLoS. One* 14 (2019) 1–23, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0226760>.
- H.J. Choo, E.J. Kim, S.Y. Kim, Y. Lee, B.G. Kim, J.H. Ahn, Microbial synthesis of hydroxytyrosol and hydroxysalidroside, *Appl. Biol. Chem.* 61 (2018) 295–301, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13765-018-0360-x>.
- J. Yao, Y. He, N. Su, S.R. Bharath, Y. Tao, J.M. Jin, W. Chen, H. Song, S.Y. Tang, Developing a highly efficient hydroxytyrosol whole-cell catalyst by de-bottlenecking rate-limiting steps, *Nat. Commun.* 11 (2020) 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-14918-5>.
- R.G. Harrison, S.R. Rudge, D.P. Petrides, *Bioseparations Science and Engineering*, 2003. ISBN 0195123409.
- J. Tang, J. Wang, P. Gong, H. Zhang, M. Zhang, C. Qi, G. Chen, C. Wang, W. Chen, Biosynthesis and biotechnological synthesis of hydroxytyrosol, *Foods*. (2024) 13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13111694>.
- M.L. Soto, A. Moure, H. Domínguez, J.C. Parajó, Recovery, concentration and purification of phenolic compounds by adsorption: a review, *J. Food Eng.* 105 (2011) 1–27, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2011.02.010>.
- D. Versteheyte, K. Binemans, T. Van Gerven, Recent advancements in centrifugal contactor design for chemical processing, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Eng.* 47 (2024) 101084, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coche.2024.101084>.
- X. Jing, P. Ning, H. Cao, J. Wang, Z. Sun, A review of application of annular centrifugal contactors in aspects of mass transfer and operational security, *Hydrometallurgy* 177 (2018) 41–48, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hydromet.2018.02.005>.
- Vedantam, S.; Joshi, J.B. Annular centrifugal contactors — A review. 2006, 522–542, [10.1205/cherd.05219](https://doi.org/10.1205/cherd.05219).
- Hamamah, Z.A.; Gru, T. Liquid-Liquid centrifugal extractors : types and recent applications – a review. 2022, 286–318, [10.1002/cben.202100035](https://doi.org/10.1002/cben.202100035).

- [38] Wang, W.; Zhang, P.; Ou, J.; Liu, F.; Tang, K.; Xu, W. Selective extraction of ECG from tea polyphenols by one step in centrifugal contactor separators : modeling and application. 2019, [10.1021/acs.iecr.8b06042](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.8b06042).
- [39] Duan, W.; Zhou, X.; Zhou, J. Extraction of caffeine with annular centrifugal contactors. 2007, 6299, [10.1080/07366290500463997](https://doi.org/10.1080/07366290500463997).
- [40] M. Bojczuk, D. Żyżelewicz, P. Hodoruk, Centrifugal partition chromatography – A review of recent applications and some classic references, *J. Sep. Sci.* 40 (2017) 1597–1609, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201601221>.
- [41] Hubert Jane, M.H. Karen Ple, J.-H.R., Polyphenol purification by solid support-free liquid–liquid chromatography (CCC, CPC), *Nat. Prod. Phytochem. Bot. Metab. Alkaloids, Phenolics Terpenes* (2013) 1–4242, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22144-6>.
- [42] T. Michel, E. Destandau, C. Elfakir, New advances in countercurrent chromatography and centrifugal partition chromatography: focus on coupling strategy, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 406 (2014) 957–969, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-013-7017-8>.
- [43] S.T. Pannakal, J. Eilstein, J. Hubert, A. Kotland, A. Prasad, A. Gueguinat-Prevot, F. Juchaux, F. Beaumard, G. Seru, S. John, et al., Rapid chemical profiling of *Filipendula ulmaria* using CPC fractionation, 2-D mapping of 13C NMR data, and high-resolution LC–MS, *Molecules* 28 (2023) 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28176349>.
- [44] K.D. Yoon, Y.W. Chin, J. Kim, Centrifugal partition chromatography: application to natural products in 1994–2009, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol.* 33 (2010) 1208–1254, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826076.2010.484374>.
- [45] A. Agalias, P. Magiatis, A.L. Skaltsounis, E. Mikros, A. Tsaropoulos, E. Gikas, I. Spanos, T. Manios, A new process for the management of olive oil mill waste water and recovery of natural antioxidants, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 55 (2007) 2671–2676, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf063091d>.
- [46] M.L. Pizarro, M. Becerra, A. Sayago, M. Beltrán, R. Beltrán, Comparison of different extraction methods to determine phenolic compounds in Virgin olive oil, *Food Anal. Methods* 6 (2013) 123–132, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12161-012-9420-8>.
- [47] A. Angelis, M. Hamzaoui, N. Aliagiannis, T. Nikou, D. Michailidis, P. Gerolimatos, A. Termentzi, J. Hubert, M. Halabalaki, J.H. Renault, et al., An integrated process for the recovery of high added-value compounds from olive oil using solid support free liquid-liquid extraction and chromatography techniques, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1491 (2017) 126–136, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2017.02.046>.
- [48] Vedantam, S.; Wardle, K.E.; Tamhane, T.V.; Ranade, V.V.; Joshi, J.B. CFD simulation of annular centrifugal extractors. 2012, 2012, [10.1155/2012/759397](https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/759397).
- [49] Jr, J.F.B.; Mcfarlane, J.; Hunt, R.D.; Luo, H.; Depaoli, W.; Schuh, D.L.; Dai, S.; Birdwell, J.F.; Mcfarlane, J.; Hunt, R.D.; et al. Separation of ionic liquid dispersions in centrifugal solvent extraction contactors Separation of ionic liquid dispersions in centrifugal solvent extraction contactors. 2007, 6395, [10.1080/01496390600745719](https://doi.org/10.1080/01496390600745719).
- [50] J. Rydberg *Solvent Extraction Principles and Practice, Revised and Expanded*; ISBN 0203021460.
- [51] A. Angelis, D. Michailidis, L. Antoniadis, P. Stathopoulos, V. Tsantila, J. M. Nuzillard, J.H. Renault, L.A. Skaltsounis, Pilot continuous centrifugal liquid-liquid extraction of extra virgin olive oil biophenols and gram-scale recovery of pure oleocanthal, oleacein, MFOA, MFLA and hydroxytyrosol, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 255 (2021) 117692, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2020.117692>.
- [52] D. Michailidis, A. Angelis, N. Aliagiannis, S. Mitakou, L. Skaltsounis, Recovery of sesamin, sesamol, and minor lignans from sesame oil using solid support-free liquid-liquid extraction and chromatography techniques and evaluation of their enzymatic inhibition properties, *Front. Pharmacol.* 10 (2019) 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2019.00723>.
- [53] Xu, J.; Duan, W.; Zhou, X.; Zhou, J. Extraction of phenol in wastewater with annular centrifugal contactors. 2006, 131, 98–102, [10.1016/j.jhazmat.2005.09.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2005.09.011).
- [54] A. López-Yerena, I. Domínguez-López, A. Vallverdú-Queralt, M. Pérez, O. Jáuregui, E. Escríbano-Ferrer, R.M. Lamuela-Raventós, Metabolomics technologies for the identification and quantification of dietary phenolic compound metabolites: an overview, *Antioxidants* 10 (2021) 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10060846>.
- [55] J.H. Renault, J.M. Nuzillard, G. Le Crouérou, P. Thépenier, M. Zèches-Hanrot, L. Le Men-Olivier, Isolation of indole alkaloids from *Catharanthus roseus* by centrifugal partition chromatography in the pH-zone refining mode, *J. Chromatogr. A* 849 (1999) 421–431, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(99\)00495-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(99)00495-1).
- [56] A. Kotland, S. Chollet, C. Diard, J.M. Autret, J. Meucci, J.H. Renault, L. Marchal, Industrial case study on alkaloids purification by pH-zone refining centrifugal partition chromatography, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1474 (2016) 59–70, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2016.10.039>.
- [57] Y. Zhou, C. Wang, R. Wang, L. Lin, Z. Yin, H. Hu, Q. Yang, Q. Zhang, Preparative separation of four sesquiterpenoids from *Curcuma longa* by high-speed countercurrent chromatography, *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 52 (2017) 497–503, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2016.1251461>.
- [58] H.R. Adhami, M. Zehl, C. Dangl, D. Dorfmeister, M. Stadler, E. Urban, P. Hewitson, S. Ignatova, L. Krenn, Preparative isolation of oleocanthal, tyrosol, and hydroxytyrosol from olive oil by HPCCC, *Food Chem.* 170 (2015) 154–159, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.08.079>.
- [59] A. Angelis, L. Antoniadis, P. Stathopoulos, M. Halabalaki, L.A. Skaltsounis, Oleocanthal and oleaceic acids: new compounds from Extra Virgin Olive Oil (EVOO), *Phytochem. Lett.* 26 (2018) 190–194, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2018.06.020>.
- [60] G.G. Leitão, F. Das Neves Costa, F. De Souza Figueiredo, Strategies of solvent system selection for the isolation of natural products by countercurrent chromatography, *Med. Plants Biodivers. Drugs* (2012) 641–668, <https://doi.org/10.1201/b12527-22>.
- [61] L. Li, J. Zhao, T. Yang, B. Sun, High-speed countercurrent chromatography as an efficient technique for large separation of plant polyphenols: a review, *Food Res. Int.* 153 (2022) 110956, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2022.110956>.
- [62] K. Li, W. Zhu, Q. Fu, Y. Ke, Y. Jin, X. Liang, Purification of amide alkaloids from *Piper longum* L. using preparative two-dimensional normal-phase liquid chromatography × reversed-phase liquid chromatography, *Analyst* 138 (2013) 3313–3320, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3an00016h>.
- [63] Q. Fu, Z. Guo, X. Zhang, Y. Liu, X. Liang, Comprehensive characterization of *Stevia Rebaudiana* using two-dimensional reversed-phase liquid chromatography/hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography, *J. Sep. Sci.* 35 (2012) 1821–1827, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201101103>.
- [64] Guo, X.; Zhang, X.; Feng, J.; Guo, Z. Purification of saponins from leaves of *Panax notoginseng* using preparative two-dimensional reversed-phase liquid chromatography /hydrophilic interaction chromatography. 2013, 3413–3421, [10.1007/s00216-013-6721-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-013-6721-8).
- [65] A. Olmo-Cunillera, A. López-Yerena, J. Lozano-Castellón, A. Tresserra-Rimbau, A. Vallverdú-Queralt, M. Pérez, NMR spectroscopy: a powerful tool for the analysis of polyphenols in extra virgin olive oil, *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 100 (2020) 1842–1851, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.10173>.
- [66] C. Fytilli, T. Nikou, N. Tentolouris, I.K. Tseti, C. Dimosthenopoulos, P.P. Sfrikakis, D. Simos, A. Kokkinos, A.L. Skaltsounis, N. Katsilambros, et al., Effect of long-term hydroxytyrosol administration on body weight, fat mass and urine metabolomics: a randomized double-blind prospective Human study, *Nutr* 14 (2022).
- [67] J.I. Mosele, S. Martín-Peláez, A. Macià, M. Farrás, R.M. Valls, Ú. Catalán, M. J. Motilva, Faecal microbial metabolism of olive oil phenolic compounds: in vitro and in vivo approaches, *Mol. Nutr. Food Res.* 58 (2014) 1809–1819, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201400124>.
- [68] R. Domínguez-Perles, D. Auñón, F. Ferreres, A. Gil-Izquierdo, Gender differences in plasma and urine metabolites from Sprague–Dawley rats after oral administration of normal and high doses of hydroxytyrosol, hydroxytyrosol acetate, and DOPAC, *Eur. J. Nutr.* 56 (2017) 215–224, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-015-1071-2>.
- [69] J.A. González-Correa, M.D. Navas, J. Muñoz-Marin, M. Trujillo, J. Fernández-Bolaños, J.P. De La Cruz, Effects of hydroxytyrosol and hydroxytyrosol acetate administration to rats on platelet function compared to acetylsalicylic acid, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 56 (2008) 7872–7876, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf801502z>.
- [70] J.A. González Correa, J.A. López-Villodres, R. Asensi, J.L. Espartero, G. Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, J.P. De La Cruz, Virgin olive oil polyphenol hydroxytyrosol acetate inhibits in vitro platelet aggregation in human whole blood: comparison with hydroxytyrosol and acetylsalicylic acid, *Br. J. Nutr.* 101 (2009) 1157–1164, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114508061539>.
- [71] Fernández-bolaños, J.G.; López, Ó.; López-garcía, M.Á.; Marset, A. Biological properties of hydroxytyrosol and its derivatives. 2010.
- [72] M. Aparicio-Soto, S. Sánchez-Fidalgo, A. González-Benjumea, I. Maya, J. G. Fernández-Bolaños, Alarcón-de-la-Lastra, C. Naturally occurring hydroxytyrosol derivatives: hydroxytyrosyl acetate and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylglycol modulate inflammatory response in murine peritoneal macrophages. Potential utility as new dietary supplements, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 63 (2015) 836–846, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf503357s>.
- [73] J.A. González-Correa, M.D. Navas, J.A. Lopez-Villodres, M. Trujillo, J.L. Espartero, J.P. De La Cruz, Neuroprotective effect of hydroxytyrosol and hydroxytyrosol acetate in rat brain slices subjected to hypoxia-reoxygenation, *Neurosci. Lett.* 446 (2008) 143–146, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2008.09.022>.
- [74] S. Sánchez-Fidalgo, I. Villegas, M. Aparicio-Soto, A. Cárdeno, M.Á. Rosillo, A. González-Benjumea, A. Marset, Ó. López, I. Maya, J.G. Fernández-Bolaños, et al., Effects of dietary virgin olive oil polyphenols: hydroxytyrosyl acetate and 3, 4-dihydroxyphenylglycol on DSS-induced acute colitis in mice, *J. Nutr. Biochem.* 26 (2015) 513–520, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnutbio.2014.12.001>.
- [75] H. Luo, Y. Li, J. Xie, C. Xu, Z. Zhang, M. Li, B. Xia, Z. Shi, L. Lin, Effect and mechanism of *Prunella vulgaris* L. extract on alleviating lipopolysaccharide-induced acute mastitis in protecting the blood-milk barrier and reducing inflammation, *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 328 (2024) 117998, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2024.117998>.
- [76] I. Kumar, R. Sharma, R. Kumar, R. Kumar, U. Sharma, C70 Fullerene-catalyzed metal-free photocatalytic ipso-hydroxylation of aryl boronic acids: synthesis of phenols, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 360 (2018) 2013–2019, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsc.201701573>.
- [77] Siebert, M.; Severin, K.; Heide, L. Formation of 4-hydroxybenzoate in *Escherichia coli*: characterization of the ubiC gene and its encoded enzyme chorismate pyruvate-lyase. 1977, 897–904.
- [78] Z. Hou, Z. Liang, Y. Li, F. Su, J. Chen, X. Zhang, D. Yang, Quantitative determination and validation of four phenolic acids in *Salvia Miltiorrhiza* Bunge using 1H-NMR spectroscopy, *Curr. Pharm. Anal.* 17 (2019) 509–519, <https://doi.org/10.12174/1573412916666191231104909>.
- [79] K. Sidoryk, K. Filip, P. Cmoch, M. Laszcz, M. Cybulski, Efficient synthesis and physicochemical characterization of natural danshensu, its S isomer and intermediates thereof, *J. Mol. Struct.* 1153 (2018) 135–148, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2017.09.118>.
- [80] Zhang, W.; Yi, W.-B. Cascade reactions. 2019, 15–26, [10.1007/978-3-030-22596-4_3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22596-4_3).
- [81] N.T.T. Thuy, H.T.M. Hien, N.C. Ha, L.T. Thom, D.D. Hong, N.Van Thinh, N.T. Dan, N.D. Hoi, V.T. Loan, H.D.; Quang, et al., Chemical constituents from the heterotrophic marine microalgae *aurantiochytrium* sp. SC145 and their antimicrobial activities, *Nat. Prod. Res.* 38 (2024) 789–795, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2023.2201882>.

- [82] X.P. Peng, Y. Wang, P.P. Liu, K. Hong, H. Chen, X. Yin, W.M. Zhu, Aromatic compounds from the halotolerant fungal strain of *Wallemia sebi* PXP-89 in a hypersaline medium, *Arch. Pharm. Res.* 34 (2011) 907–912, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12272-011-0607-0>.
- [83] Y.M. Yan, H.Q. Dai, Y. Du, B. Schneider, H. Guo, D.P. Li, L.X. Zhang, H. Fu, X. P. Dong, Y.X. Cheng, Identification of blapsins A and B as potent small-molecule 14-3-3 inhibitors from the insect *Blaps japonensis*, *Bioorganic Med. Chem. Lett.* 22 (2012) 4179–4181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2012.04.027>.
- [84] A. Bianco, F. Cocioli, M. Guiso, Dipartimento the occurrence in olive oil of a new class of phenolic compounds: hydroxy-isochromans, *Food Chem.* 77 (2001) 405–411, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146\(01\)00366-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146(01)00366-1).
- [85] Ajal El Amine, Chaji Salah, R.N. Sanae Moussafir, A.S. Bajjoub, *Virgin olive oil phenolic compounds: insights on their occurrence, health-promoting properties and bioavailability*, *Intech i* (2012) 13.
- [86] P. Lorenz, M. Zeh, J. Martens-Lobenhoffer, H. Schmidt, G. Wolf, T.F.W. Horn, Natural and newly synthesized hydroxy-1-aryl-isochromans: a class of potential antioxidants and radical scavengers, *Free Radic. Res.* 39 (2005) 535–545, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10715760500073733>.
- [87] R. Bernini, M.S. Gilardini Montani, N. Merendino, A. Romani, F. Velotti, Hydroxytyrosol-derived compounds: a basis for the creation of new pharmacological agents for cancer prevention and therapy, *J. Med. Chem.* 58 (2015) 9089–9107, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.5b00669>.
- [88] I. Gouvinhas, N. Machado, C. Sobreira, R. Domínguez-Perles, S. Gomes, E. Rosa, A. I.R.N.A. Barros, Critical review on the significance of Olive phytochemicals in plant physiology and human health, *Molecules* 22 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22111986>.
- [89] R. Mateos, A. Madrona, G. Pereira-Caro, V. Domínguez, R.M. Cert, J. Parrado, B. Sarriá, L. Bravo, J.L. Espartero, Synthesis and antioxidant evaluation of isochroman-derivatives of hydroxytyrosol: structure-activity relationship, *Food Chem.* 173 (2015) 313–320, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.10.036>.
- [90] Nmr, C. Cyclo(pro-tyr) from an endophytic rhizobium isolated from. 2012, 47, 902–903.
- [91] R. Liu, H. Li, J. Yang, 2,5-Diketopiperazines from *Aspergillus* sp., the endophytic Fungus of *astragalus membranaceus* and their anticancer Assay, *Chem. Nat. Compd.* 56 (2020) 583–585, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10600-020-03100-4>.
- [92] B. Paudel, R. Maharjan, P. Rajbhandari, N. Aryal, S. Aziz, K. Bhattarai, B. Baral, R. Malla, H.D. Bhattarai, Maculosin, a non-toxic antioxidant compound isolated from *Streptomyces* sp. KTM18, *Pharm. Biol.* 59 (2021) 933–936, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13880209.2021.1946091>.
- [93] A.C. Stierle, J.H. Cardellina, G.A. Strobel, Maculosin, a host-specific phytotoxin for spotted knapweed from *Alternaria alternata*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 85 (1988) 8008–8011, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.85.21.8008>.
- [94] Xu, Y.; Liang, X.; Kim, H. In Vitro and In Silico studies of maculosin as a melanogenesis and tyrosinase inhibitor. 2025.
- [95] Isolation and identification of maculosins from *Streptomyces rochei* 87051-3.
- [96] D. Yang, S.Y. Park, Y.S. Park, H. Eun, S.Y. Lee, Metabolic engineering of *Escherichia coli* for natural product biosynthesis, *Trends Biotechnol.* 38 (2020) 745–765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2019.11.007>.
- [97] H. Chen, L. Wang, *Sugar Strategies for Biomass Biochemical Conversion*, Metallurgical Industry Press, 2017.
- [98] X. Wu, J. Liu, D. Liu, M. Yuwen, M.A.G. Koffas, J. Zha, Biosynthesis of eriodictyol from tyrosine by *Corynebacterium glutamicum*, *Microb. Cell Fact.* 21 (2022) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12934-022-01815-3>.
- [99] M.A. Prieto, A. Perez-Aranda, J.L. Garcia, Characterization of an *Escherichia coli* aromatic hydroxylase with a broad substrate range, *J. Bacteriol.* 175 (1993) 2162–2167, <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.175.7.2162-2167.1993>.